

HOW BANKS CAN INVEST IN SUSTAINABILITY (IN THE CASE OF AFRICA)

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RESEARCH PROPOSAL

Rationale

Experts have asserted that ecological sustainability is the biggest global challenge and that there is a need to collectively stop human-made devastation to nature and come forward to make a sustainable environmental policy in order to avoid some of these unfortunate climate effects. In e-commerce perspective, green banking can enhance the environmental sustainability by ensuring that online banking and e-banking by following the 3D approach- De-materialization, De-carbonization, and De-mobilization in the daily activities of the bank (Hossen et al., 2014).

Keywords: African banking, Sustainability, Green banking , Green financing, Investment

1. Introduction

Traditionally banks sustainability was partly dependent on the fragility in the corporate governance in the banking industry and global financial crisis and as a result excessive risk taking was tightly looked-into to intensified the significance of banks insolvency and liquidity risk. Fast forward, our world is being attacked by our own selves, human activities such as cutting plants, polluting air and water and testing atomic energy as the symbol of technological advancement and the industrial revolution are harming the same nature. Subsequently nature also takes some sort of revenge in the form of numerous calamities like storms, floods, droughts, earthquake, excessive heat and melting ice. Experts have asserted that ecological sustainability is the biggest global challenge and that there is a need to collectively stop human-made devastation to nature and come forward to make a sustainable environmental policy in order to avoid some of these unfortunate climate effects. In e-commerce perspective, green banking can enhance the environmental sustainability by ensuring that online banking and e-banking by following the 3D approach- De-materialization, De-carbonization, and De-mobilization in the daily activities of the bank (Hossen et al., 2014). Any environmental-unfriendly activities and substantial use of energy that raises the carbon footprints of banks needs to be halted. Consequently, to minimize carbon footprints and ensure sustainable environment banks are motivated to use eco-friendly technology, green products, new process and strategies (Bhardwaj and Malhotra, 2013). Green banking avoids usage of paper as much as possible and relies on online/electronic transactions for processing so that we can get green credit cards and green mortgages. Less paperwork means less cutting of trees which can preserve the environmental sustainability (Singh and Singh, 2012). Banks as a key society

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player and other corporations must have some responsibilities to reduce the carbon emission and help the government to minimize this by introducing Green Banking for sustainable development. Green lending policies and commitment of banks can in favor of the fortification of environment and ensure eco friendly projects (Mani, 2011). However, the sustainability of environment is a pressing issue that requires detailed studies with focus on African perspective according to this study objective. This proposal is motivated by the environmental sustainability issues (World Bank Group Roadmap) and sustainable investment inclusive, the paper will study in detail banks green financing, and interaction between environmental financing and performance, and finally, how banks can prioritize investment in green banking era.

2. Research Objectives

The study mainly aims at understanding the concepts of green banking and the need for banks to give priority to sustainable investment through different literature reviews with focus on;

1. Awareness campaign among the African economies about the e-banking, paperless banking, mobile banking, and online banking, etc. through green banking concept;
2. To ascertain diverse levels of green banking ingenuities, its strategies, and practices in Africa and even across the world;
3. Highlighting the accomplishment of green banking practices in the western countries and how it's helping in the environmental sustainability.
4. Pinpointing some of the immediate challenges in implementing the green banking activities and to suggest some solution to overcoming those challenges going into future.
5. Ensuring sustainable financing for environmental services and new environmental strategies in the African countries.
6. Empirically assess the theories concerning green financing and sustainability.

3. Research Questions

This paper aims to investigate how climate change has impacted on green financing, sustainable investment and banks performance and in both sustainable and unsustainable environments scenarios. By answering the following question; 1. Whether climate change is impacting on banks investment approach? 2. How environmental financing impacts on environmental sustainability and banks performance?

4. Scope of the Study

The scope of this study will cover analyzing of theories on green financing, banks investment and sustainability and the World Bank Group roadmap charter on environmental sustainability. Specifically, going deeper on how banks can make sustainable investment with particular interest in environmental financing mechanisms and the new environmental strategies. Also, the interaction between sustainable environment and banks investment shift. Banks are aware of the environmental changes and being social players could try to support and supplement the

government effort towards substantial reduction in carbon emission all over the world through introducing the green banking or sustainable banking practices.

5. Significance of the Study

This study will be of significance to couple of stakeholders. Firstly, the banking industry, investors, financial institutions, global civil societies, environmentalists, global institutions, add-up to knowledge body and scientific research in academia and the African economy as a whole. Lastly, the study's recommendations that could ensure sustainable financing of environmental services in Africa, and national environmental finance strategies and to improve effective monitoring of the impacts of environmental finance.

6. Literature Review

As a matter of facts other research works on this same or similar topic area will be examined. In general terms „Green Banking“ is a multifaceted activity of banks concerning about environmental issues in their daily activities and investment as well. This bank has a positive social and ecological impact at its heart as well as its economic sustainability. Green banking or sustainable banking can help the business and society by saving time, energy and cost. It reduces paperwork, creates awareness to business people regarding the environment of the greater society (Bahl, 2012). Socially responsible banking activities start with the aim of protecting the environment; before granting any loan for any project at first, this banks consider the environmental aspects of the project, at present or even in future environmental safety (Bihari, 2011). As environment has direct effect to the business assets quality, profit, rate of return, human capital and some other aspects, so the banks should play proactive role to go green by considering ecological and environmental issues in their lending principles (Sahoo and Nayak, 2007). According to (Biswas ,2011) green banking rationalizes the uses of paper and minimizes the cost by practicing online banking, internet banking, mobile banking, SMS banking and ATM services. (Dharwal and Agarwal 2013) argued that green banking or ethical banking is a key to mitigate different types of risks like- the credit risk, legal risk, and reputation risk. (Goyal and Joshi, 2011) highlighted some social and ethical issues in banking like- disbursement of loan only to those organizations which have environmental concerns and finally, it can facilitate the achievement of sustainable development of banking and financial sector.

7. 0 Data, Research Methodology and Limitation

7 .1 Data & Methodology

This research will employ qualitative and exploratory research methodology of a panel data, primary and secondary data will be obtained. Secondary data collection technique will be used to collect data and information as proposed by (Bergh and Ketchen, 2009). In this research, the potential information sources will be obtained from available database, research papers, company websites, annual report of the company. Also, an extensive literature survey and possible interview with banks officials and environmentalists.

7.2 Limitations to the Study

The researcher might encounter some basic limitations during the research regarding the authenticity of sources, reliability and validity of collected information, such as non-availability data on banks portfolio and wished set of information, and completing the research in limited time and cost. However, with all these constraints, all attempts would make to undertake a valid and comprehensive study.

8. Empirical results, findings and conclusion

This section will summarize the results, discuss the findings and draw conclusions based on the findings.

9. References and Appendix

This section is dedicated to acknowledge other research materials aiding this work and also the appendix will be the quick library where some of the tables, figures, charts etc could be found for verification.

10. References

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